

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

ROLE EVALUATION: THE ACUTE CARE NURSE PRACTITIONER LEADING
MULTI-DISCIPLINARY ROUNDS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Lisa Marie Evans

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Thomas W. Barkley, Jr., PhD, ACNP-BC, FAANP, Project Chair
Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN, Committee Member

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ABSTRACT

The role of the nurse practitioner is unique to the healthcare industry. With advanced knowledge and training, the utilization of the nurse practitioner has been incorporated into multiple settings nationwide. However, there is still growing concern that the role of the nurse practitioner is not clearly understood. Through a better understanding of the specific components and functions of the nurse practitioner role, in relation to patient outcomes, new and innovative uses for the nurse practitioner role can be employed. As more nurse practitioners assume an increasing role in the provision of care to patients within the acute care setting, the role of the acute care nurse practitioner has emerged as an innovative tactic to improve health care delivery systems. New opportunities have arisen for the incorporation of the acute care nurse practitioner into different healthcare delivery models: One such model is multi-disciplinary rounding. A new innovation for the structure of multi-disciplinary rounding is the incorporation of the acute care nurse practitioner as the lead for this collaborative care practice model. To better understand the impact on patient outcomes and quality of care measures, a thorough understanding of the specific role components and functions of the acute care nurse practitioner is necessary. This project evaluates the role of the acute care nurse practitioner as the lead for multi-disciplinary rounds within an intensive care step-down unit.

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BACKGROUND

The healthcare system within the United States is currently at a cross roads for the development of a new definition of healthcare for the future. In 2010, Congress enacted the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act (PPACA) as the first step toward healthcare reform within the United States. This comprehensive legislation is leading the transformation of the healthcare system as we know it. The primary goals of the PPACA are to increase the number of Americans with healthcare insurance coverage and to decrease the exponential cost of health care (The Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation, 2013). The PPACA supports the revision of the current healthcare framework to a more comprehensive patient-centered model, with the promotion of disease prevention and the expectation that evidence-based practice interventions be utilized to improve patient outcomes. The PPACA provisions are designed to encourage quality of care and decrease overall healthcare expenditures through the improvement of patient outcomes. Further, this initiative has focused on the provision of affordable, quality care that is accessible to all individuals within the United States.

The Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act

The comprehensive healthcare reform of the PPACA includes provisions that focus on stronger consumer rights and protections, more affordable coverage, better access to care, and building of a stronger Medicare system (The Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation, 2013; United States Department of Health and Human Services [USDHHS], 2013). With nearly 50 million Americans currently utilizing Medicare services and a total expenditure of 549.1 billion dollars spent in 2011 by Medicare, reform in this area has become a critical focus (The Medicare Payment Advisory Commission, 2012). With

that in mind, the goals of the PPACA in support of a stronger Medicare system include measures aimed at adding new services, fighting against fraud, and decreasing costs in an effort to improve care coordination and quality of care (The Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation, 2013; USDHHS, 2013).

Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services

In response to the PPACA initiatives, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) realigned their objectives to parallel those of the PPACA. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services focused its evaluation on the reformation of inpatient hospital stays, in an effort to decrease cost and improve quality of care (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services [CMS], 2012). In 2010, the largest share of total healthcare dollars was spent on inpatient hospital stays, with two-thirds of the costs spent on adults aged 65–84 (Agency for Healthcare Research & Quality [AHRQ], 2013). This amounted to approximately \$375.9 billion dollars allocated to acute care episodes with an average cost of \$9,700 per inpatient hospital stay (AHRQ, 2013). Medicare accounted for half of the aggregate inpatient hospital costs and paid, on average, a higher cost per stay of \$11,600 for hospitalizations (AHRQ, 2013).

Due to the exponential costs associated with inpatient hospital stays, in 2011, CMS updated and finalized new rules for payment policies and rates (Pugliese, 2012). These new rules incorporated three areas, of the PPACA specific to patient care, in which inpatient facilities will be evaluated based on performance rates against a set national benchmark. These areas include Hospital-Value Based Purchasing (VBP), Hospital-Acquired Conditions (HAC), and Hospital-Inpatient Quality Reporting (IQR). The PPACA mandates that hospitals be reimbursed on performance measured by VBP, HAC,

and IQR (Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services [CMS], 2013). The new payment structure requires that hospitals perform at or above the set national benchmarks to continue to earn CMS payments (CMS, 2012). Failure to perform at benchmark levels in the designated areas results in percentage reductions in payments for inpatient services (CMS, 2012; Pugliese, 2012).

As a result of these reforms, the traditional healthcare payment system has been transformed from a traditional *fee-for-service* structure to a *pay-for-performance* structure. In alignment with the PPACA, CMS no longer supports the quantity of services provided but rather the quality of services provided. The pay-for-performance structure has emerged as a way to focus on quality patient outcomes and decrease the cost of care (Pugliese, 2012). As a means to quantify quality care, inpatient institutions are now evaluated on quality measure outcomes supported by VBP (CMS, 2012). Further CMS partnered with The Joint Commission (TJC) to collaboratively develop what has become known as the “core measures” in a concerted effort to quantify quality of care (The Joint Commission [TJC], 2010). These core measures were developed to monitor clinical processes and ensure that patients received the recommended care (The Joint Commission [TJC], 2013a). These uniform core performance measures are considered the “gold standard” treatment in healthcare.

The Core Measures

In an effort to improve patient care, CMS collaborated with TJC to embark on a national quality initiative to standardize and monitor clinical process as well as provide recommended care that is evidenced-based in nature (TJC, 2010). Together, a set of core measures were developed to include different areas specific to inpatient hospital

admissions. These core measures include standardized interventions with recommended care activities for the diagnoses with the highest associated morbidity, mortality, and cost across the nation. These care areas include treatment for acute myocardial infarction (AMI), heart failure (HF), pneumonia (PNA), post-operative surgical care or surgical care improvement process (SCIP), emergency department throughput measure for admitted patients, and global immunizations (The Joint Commission [TJC], 2013b). Under each core measure, specific clinical indicators based on the latest evidence have been identified and incorporated as part of the core measure to reflect evidence best practice (TJC, 2013b). Failure by hospitals to address a set measure for each patient admitted with a diagnosis of AMI, HF, PNA, or SCIP results in a failure in the core measure for that particular encounter, leading to decreased reimbursements from CMS.

Currently, the basis for the VBP program focuses on hospital performance on 25 different measures related to clinical process measures and patients' experience of care (Kapu & Kleinpell, 2013), of which six categories are considered a core measure for clinical process of care measures. Performance on the core measures is utilized to evaluate the quality of care provided against a national benchmark and determine financial payment from the CMS. Inpatient hospitals are mandated to report routinely and evaluate their performance as a means of continuous, internal quality improvement (TJC, 2013b). Evaluation of the data and the performance metrics across the nation are then utilized to improve the healthcare delivery process at both the institutional and national level (TJC, 2013b).

Improvement of Healthcare Delivery

The improvement of healthcare delivery is a national aim focused on the provision of quality care to all individuals. The current healthcare reform initiatives have forced institutions across the nation to ensure that they are providing quality care evidenced in part, by performance on the core measures. Hospitals are now faced with a difficult challenge of improving measurable quality outcomes and evaluating fiscal concerns (O'Mahony, Mazur, Charney, Wang, & Fine, 2007). The financial success and future survival of hospitals is currently dependent on their ability to drive improvements in quality care at a reduced cost (Gannon & Becker, 2013).

According to Ellrodt et al. (2007) hospitals are confronted with developing implementation systems that will be able to sustain improved clinical care for the future. This has forced the acute healthcare industry to look at new and innovative ways to achieve improved patient outcomes. Strategies include the development and implementation of systems designed to achieve high performance on VBP initiatives. According to Cortes, Landman, and Smoldt (2012) the key to higher value care is achieving good patient outcomes with less utilization of resources. In an effort to operationalize the vision of the new healthcare model, the Institute of Medicine (IOM, 2010) has identified improved care coordination as a mechanism to achieving high performance on VBP initiatives. As the model has shifted to a patient-centered, preventative model, in which improved patient care coordination and outcomes are key, collaboration among all healthcare team members is imperative. This has stimulated the transformation of healthcare delivery and has forced institutions and leaders across the nation to reevaluate and redesign process of care to promote interprofessional

collaboration throughout the continuum with everyone, including nurses (Robert Wood Johnson Foundation [RWJF], 2013).

Interdisciplinary Care

With the focus on interdisciplinary care, the standards mandate that patient care, treatment, and rehabilitation be planned, evaluated, and revised throughout the continuum of care by an interdisciplinary collaborative team (Institute for Healthcare Improvement [IHI], 2010). The premise to interdisciplinary teams is integration of the care delivery system to maximize potential outcomes of care (Kilgore & Langford, 2009).

Interdisciplinary teams have been conceptualized as different professionals working in parallel to bring their respective expertise to the group to provide a more integrated care delivery system (Kilgore & Langford, 2009). With this in mind, acute care institutions are rapidly seeking innovative tactics to address the incorporation of interdisciplinary practice into the daily routine care of patients. One of the emerging tactics supported by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI, 2010) is the development and embodiment of multidisciplinary rounds within an acute care setting.

Multidisciplinary Rounds

Multidisciplinary rounds (MDRs) are defined as a patient-centered model of care that emphasizes safety along with efficiency, and enables multiple disciplines to participate in the patient's care through recommendations based on clinical expertise (IHI, 2010). According to the IHI (2010), MDRs is an effective way to improve quality, safety, and the overall patient experience through increased coordination of care. The use of MDRs in an acute care setting has shown improvement in patient outcomes through increased communication, as well as identification and assessment of best practice

initiatives (Wilson, Newman, & Ilari, 2009). MDRs have also been shown to improve communication and collaboration with adherence to process measures, better patient outcomes, improved compliance with protocols, as well as decreases in adverse events, lengths of stay, cost of care, and lower mortality rates (Kim, Barnato, Angus, Fleisher, & Kahn, 2010; Vazirani, Hays, Shapiro, & Cowan, 2005). Multi-disciplinary rounds have been adopted as a successful method that improves efficiency and communication among the care team and leads to overall improved outcomes for patients (Institute for Healthcare Improvement [IHI], 2011; Vazirani et al., 2005).

According to Halm, Gagner, Goering, Sabo, and Smith (2003), MDRs are a method for facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration and results in “earlier identification of clinical issues, more timely referrals, implementation of preventive nursing interventions, increased communication-all leading to better clinical outcomes, increased patient/family satisfaction, and decreased length of stay” (p. 134). MDRs have been identified as a new care coordination strategy in acute care settings and the added value has been recognized in patient care, especially within an intensive care unit setting (Burger, 2007; Falise, 2007; Halm, Gagner, Goering, Sabo, & Smith, 2003; Kim et al., 2010; Vazirani et al., 2005). Currently, MDRs are being utilized in acute care settings to address patient care issues and improve coordination of care. Institutions are beginning to evaluate process care measures, including length of stay, timely discharges, efficiency, and delivery of evidenced based care as a means for quality improvement (O’Mahony et al., 2007).

Structured MDRs are paramount to meeting the demands of interdisciplinary practice models and are highly recommended as strategic sessions of evaluation and

planning for optimal patient care. The ideal model supported by the IHI (2010) for MDRs includes the following: MDRs occur every day and include key disciplines specific to the patient population being addressed; a designated team member to lead rounds; utilization of an individualized daily goal sheet; assessment of patient safety concerns; identification of potential transfer or discharge and potential barriers; and encouragement of participation of patient and family members. Implementation of MDRs includes the identification of who will participate in rounds, what will be specifically addressed during rounds, where and when rounds will take place, and how the MDRs will be conducted (IHI, 2011). Utilizing the IHI framework supporting MDRs, many institutions across the nation have been successful in implementing MDRs within an intensive care unit (ICU) setting (Der, 2009; Ellrodt et al., 2007; IHI, 2010; Lome, Stalnaker, Carlson, Kline & Sise, 2010; Mower-Wade & Pirrung, 2010).

Patient Outcomes

One of the critical elements of MDRs is addressing best practice initiatives and assuring adherence to evidence based guidelines. MDRs have shown a positive impact on patient outcomes as well as a decrease in cost of care. In institutions where MDRs have been incorporated, the evaluation of MDRs have shown positive patient outcomes, including overall decreased length of stay (LOS), decreased ICU LOS, lower rates of urinary tract infections and skin breakdown, shorter times to discontinuation of the Foley catheter and central line, and increased mobility (Russell, VorderBruegge, & Burns, 2002). Der (2009) reported that after the implementation of MDRs, there was a decrease in central-line blood stream infections, length of stay, mortality, and fall rates. Wilson, Newman, and Ilari (2009) reported both cost savings and a decrease in the number of

mechanical ventilation days through the use of MDRs. Although a majority of the literature has focused on MDRs and patient outcomes specific to intensive care units, other studies have evaluated the use of MDRs to improve quality outcomes and more specifically, quality core measure performance.

As hospitals across the nation are held to these quality core measures for pay-for-performance metrics, a challenge exists to develop a comprehensive approach to improve quality of care for patients. MDRs have been identified as a means to achieving improvement in quality core measure areas. The use of MDRs has also been shown to be effective in addressing institutional performance on CMS core measures (Der, 2009; O'Mahony et al., 2007; Wilson et al., 2009). A study by O'Mahony, Mazur, Charney, Wang, and Fine (2007) found a significant improvement in quality core measures for heart failure, acute myocardial infarction, and pneumonia after the implementation of MDRs. Similarly, Ellrodt et al. (2007) found improved adherence to evidence based measures by the American Heart Association's "Get With the Guidelines" (GWTGs) for stroke, heart failure, and acute myocardial infarction after the implementation of MDRs. These guidelines serve to complement the core measure sets developed by CMS and TJC and are reflective of best practice guidelines. Further, it has been identified that multi-disciplinary care coordination can improve patient satisfaction, post discharge quality of life, and decreased length of stay by 1–2 days through transitional care planning, which can reduce readmission rates up to 30% (Masica, Richter, Convery, & Haydar, 2009).

Although the use of MDRs has been incorporated into acute care settings, MDRs have traditionally been limited to and evaluated within the ICU and trauma settings (Der, 2009; Jacobowski, Girard, Mulder, & Ely, 2010; Kim et al., 2010; Lome et al., 2010;

Morris et al., (2012); Mower-Wade & Pirrung, 2010; Wilson et al., 2009). However, in a position statement by the IHI (2010), the use of MDRs outside of the ICU and trauma areas is highly encouraged. Due to the success of MDRs in the ICU setting showing improved patient outcomes and decreased lengths of stay, institutions are beginning to evaluate the potential to extend the use of MDRs outside of the ICU and trauma areas (Hoffman, Tasota, Zullo, Scharfenberg, & Donahoe, 2005). Ellrodt et al. (2007) demonstrated improved patient outcomes for patients admitted with heart failure, acute myocardial infarction, and pneumonia through the use of MDRs in telemetry units.

Despite these efforts to expand the use of MDRs outside of the ICU, there is growing concern from professional societies that a projected inability exists to meet the demands associated with expansion of MDRs to other areas within the acute care setting (Hoffman et al., 2005; IHI, 2011; Institute of Medicine [IOM], 2010). One of the emerging tactics employed to meet those demands is the use of nurse practitioners to help bridge the practice gap and deliver safe, effective, quality care (IOM, 2010; RWJF, 2013).

Nurse Practitioners

With the increased need for interdisciplinary practice to ensure improvements in healthcare delivery and patient outcomes, MDRs are visualized as a means to achieving that ideal. The role of the nurse practitioner (NP) has been increasingly used in the management of hospitalized patients and has been identified as a solution to meeting the practice gap (Kleinpell, Ely, & Grabenkort, 2008). Several studies have shown improved patient outcomes, increased communication, and collaboration of team members with the addition of a NP in an acute care setting (Kleinpell et al., 2008; Newhouse et al., 2011;

Sise et al., 2011; Vazirani et al., 2005). According to Carpenter, Gregg, Owens, Buchman, and Coopersmith (2012), acute care settings have turned toward NPs in an attempt to promote more consistent practices in patient care. Expanded reliance on NPs is valued as a complement to traditional care models to ensure continuity of care (Kleinpell et al., 2008). The use of a NP in a multidisciplinary approach in the management of patient care enhances the quality of care provided (Carpenter et al., 2012; Gannon & Becker, 2013; Kleinpell et al., 2008).

Acute Care Nurse Practitioners. Nurse practitioners are advanced practice nurses with specialty training in differing areas of practice. Specific to the inpatient environment, the role of an acute care nurse practitioner (ACNP) emerged in the early 1990s to address the needs of an advanced practice nurse with knowledge of acute and critically ill patients (Kleinpell et al., 2008). Acute care nurse practitioners have an expanded scope of practice, incorporating medical and advanced nursing functions, and provision of care in collaboration with members of the healthcare team across the continuum (Sidani & Irvine, 1999). The expanded scope of practice is considered the unique qualifier of the ACNP role that renders benefit to patients, hospitals, and the health care system (Sidani & Irvine, 1999). The role of the ACNP has been identified as a driver of change for collaborative care and accountability for patient outcomes and costs (Gannon & Becker, 2013). According to Gannon and Becker (2013), the incorporation of an ACNP into the acute care setting has demonstrated improved patient outcomes, patient satisfaction, and adherence to clinical practice guidelines, all of which are outcomes related to VBP measures. The role of the ACNP is uniquely positioned to be incorporated as an integral part of quality improvement programs and cost reductions

to assist in hospital success under VBP initiatives (Gannon & Becker, 2013). The introduction of an ACNP to collaborative models has shown decreased length of stay and cost per care episode (Meyer & Meirs, 2005), as well as improved patient satisfaction (Stables et al., 2004). A study by Hoffman, Tasota, Zullo, Schargenberg, and Donahoe (2005) demonstrated that ACNPs allotted more time to activities related to coordination of care and interaction with other disciplines, patients, and family members. Further, the use of ACNPs into multidisciplinary teams has shown increased compliance to clinical practice guidelines and quality improvement measures (Kleinpell et al., 2008). The incorporation of an ACNP can be a means to facilitating interdisciplinary practice, collaborative care planning, earlier identification of clinical issues, and more timely referrals, all leading to better clinical outcomes and decreased cost of care (Hoffman et al., 2005; Vazirani et al., 2005).

The ACNP is emerging as a leading role in the transformative healthcare delivery model. Through improved patient care collaboration, adherence to clinical practice guidelines, and improved patient and family satisfaction, the use of the ACNP as part of MDRs can be an effective strategy to improve patient outcomes. The ACNP can be an integral role in the transition of pay-for-performance mandates and can be a key player in driving improvements in quality care. The continuity of care provided by the ACNP can be a key component in the restructuring of the healthcare delivery and process outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

Currently, the healthcare system within the United States is undergoing a dramatic shift with a transition toward redefining healthcare for the future. With the implementation of the PPACA, it is now mandated that hospitals be accountable for

performance measures and patient outcomes. In line with the vision of the PPACA, CMS has restructured reimbursement for hospitals and has moved from a fee-for-service model to a pay-for-performance model based on VBP outcomes. Acute care institutions are now faced with addressing both value of care and cost reduction, and continued success and survival will now depend on the ability to drive improvements in quality of care at a reduced cost (Gannon & Becker, 2013).

To improve quality and continuity of care, the IHI (2010) has recommended the incorporation of interdisciplinary practice into the daily routine care of patients. The IHI (2010) has identified MDRs as an effective way to improve patient quality, safety, and overall patient experience through increased coordination of care. Multi-disciplinary rounds are seen as an effective tool to improve patient outcomes, address best practice initiatives, and improve adherence to core measures and evidenced based practice guidelines. However, most institutions continue to limit the use of MDRs to the ICU setting (Wilson et al., 2009). As an alternative to improving VBP adherence and ensure financial reimbursements, some institutions have incorporated nurse practitioners into MDRs and have found significant improvements in patient outcomes (Lome et al., 2010; Wilson et al., 2009). A proactive approach is to extend the use of MDRs led by a nurse practitioner to other units in the acute care setting (IHI, 2010; Vazirani et al., 2005).

As the role of the ACNP has been identified as uniquely positioned to assist hospitals in achieving high level performance and reducing costs (Gannon & Becker, 2013; Kleinpell et al., 2008), the ACNP can play a vital role in facilitating interdisciplinary practice and collaboration outside of the ICU. Despite these recommendations, there is a continued lack of use of the nurse practitioner in MDRs

outside of the ICU and there is little research to support the actual tasks performed by the nurse practitioner that have the potential to impact patient outcomes. Although many of the outcome studies to date have identified the impact of NP care, there is little information within the literature that identifies the unique components of the NP role (Kapu & Kleinpell, 2013). According to Kapu and Kleinpell (2013) examining key components of the NP role associated with outcomes of care is paramount to understanding and identifying outcomes that are impacted by NP led initiatives. It is purported that “the identification and valuing of the distinct contributions of specific nurse practitioner roles are required to clearly link nurse practitioner activities to outcomes” (Kilpatrick, Lavoie-Tremblay, Lamothe, Ritchie, & Doran, 2013, p. 206).

To further understand the impact of NP utilization, it has been recommended that NPs begin to examine key aspects of VBP initiatives that focus on performance improvement (Kapu & Kleinpell, 2013). As each ACNP role has a different focus, the role development is sensitive to the surrounding context in which the ACNP is involved (DiCenso et al., 2010). Little is known about the structures and processes occurring in healthcare teams in which ACNPs play a part and the effect on the ACNP role (Kilgore & Langford, 2010). Therefore, it is important to understand ACNP roles in the context of the role in which they have been placed (Kilpatrick et al., 2013). Understanding the specific ACNP role in relation to process contributions on the impact of patient outcomes is necessary to further define the role at both the institutional and national levels.

Supporting Framework

According to Polit and Beck (2011) conceptual frameworks help organize concepts by virtue of relevance to a common theme. A conceptual framework should broadly present the understanding of the phenomena of interest (Polit & Beck, 2011). Several conceptual frameworks have been developed to illustrate different aspects of the advanced practice nursing role (Kilpatrick et al., 2013). In response to the variation of ACNP roles across multiple settings leading to variability in outcome achievement, Sidani and Irvine (1999) developed a conceptual framework specific to the ACNP role as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for Evaluating the ACNP Role. Adapted from “A Conceptual Framework for Evaluating the Nurse Practitioner Role in Acute Care Settings,” by S. Sidani and D. Irvine, 1999, *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 30, p. 63. Copyright 1999 by Blackwell Science Ltd. Request for permission to reprint granted.

The “Conceptual Framework for Evaluating the ACNP Role” is a complex system of interrelated factors that affect role effectiveness and are present in the ACNP practice situation (Sidani & Irvine, 1999). The framework was originally adapted from the

“Nursing Role Effectiveness Model” developed by Irvine and associates. The primary goal in redefining the original framework included a need to understand the “why” and the “how” of the ACNP role and the effects on patient and cost outcomes (Sidani & Irvine, 1999). Elements of the original framework were selected that were deemed relevant to ACNP practice and the core structure, process, and outcomes components were operationalized.

Structure

Structure is referred to as patient variables, ACNP variables, and organizational variables that influence the processes and outcomes of care. Patient variables are defined as demographics of the individual patient; illness/health, which is characterized by severity of illness, medical diagnosis, and health beliefs; and resources, which are defined as access to and utilization of healthcare services. ACNP variables were operationalized as either professional or psychological characteristics specific to the ACNP. The category of ACNP professional characteristics includes level of education, type of training for the role, area of specialty and years of experience. The category of ACNP psychological variables includes ACNP perceived competence in the role, role strain, role satisfaction, and interpersonal communication skills. Organizational variables include the employment setting, clinical practice area, the extent of role formalization, the practice model, receptivity of the ACNP role by others and perceived autonomy and independence in the role.

Process

The Process component of the framework is represented by the ACNP role components, role enactment, and role functions (Sidani & Irvine, 1999). ACNP role components have been identified as clinician/practitioner, educator, researcher, and administrator. In the clinician/practitioner role, the ACNP is providing direct care to patients. As an educator, the ACNP participates in clinical education and formal education programs. The ACNP as a researcher is defined as a participant in the dissemination of research findings into clinical practice to develop practice protocols and/or project improvements as well as development of research projects. As an administrator, ACNPs participate on institutional and community committees.

Role enactment is defined as both a physician extender and an expanded nursing role. The ACNP as a physician extender is responsible for the daily medical management of patients and primarily assumes medical functions. As an expanded nursing role, the ACNP assumes both medical and expanded nursing functions working under a collaborative and interdisciplinary model.

Role function is referred to as either independent or interdependent. Under independent role functions, the ACNP is able to assume and perform tasks without medical consultation or protocols and includes diagnostic activities, such as physical examinations and taking histories; planning care activities, through prescription of nursing interventions; and care related activities such as education, counseling, and therapeutic procedures. Under interdependent role functions, the “functions assumed by the ACNP depend upon the other health care providers’ role responsibilities for their accomplishment” (Sidani & Irvine, 1999, p. 62). These are objectified by care

coordination activities such as discharge planning and collaborating with team members.

Outcomes

The outcomes component of the framework is reflective in the ACNP role goals and expectations of increased quality of care and decreased cost (Sidani & Irvine, 1999). Quality of care is operationalized as: clinical outcomes/symptom management, freedom from complications, functional status, knowledge of the disease and its treatment, and lastly, satisfaction of care. Cost of care is operationalized as costs for the patient, the institution, and the health system.

Propositions

The conceptual framework proposes that the effects of structure (patient variables, ACNP variables, and organization variables) impact the process (role components and role enactment) and outcomes (quality and cost) of the ACNP role. Further, the effects of the process (role components and role enactment) impact the outcomes (quality and cost). Lastly, Sidani and Irvine (1999) identified four process mechanisms of the direct care component of the ACNP role that facilitate positive outcomes. These mechanisms include provision of comprehensive care, ensuring continuity of care, coordination of services, and provision of care in a timely manner. This framework provides a thorough reflection of the ACNP care situation and the interrelationship of the structure and process of the ACNP role on outcomes. The Sidani and Irvine Framework provides a structural model to evaluate the ACNP role effectiveness “by linking the ACNP role enactment to patient outcomes, and captures much of the complexity of today’s healthcare environment” (Kilpatrick et al., 2013, p. 206). The concepts and precepts of this conceptual framework will be utilized to guide the development of this project.

Purpose of the Project

The aim of this project is to explore the role of the ACNP as the lead for MDRs, in an intensive care step down unit, to better understand and evaluate the distinct process and contributions of the ACNP in relation to patient outcomes. As part of a proactive approach to improve patient outcomes, St. Joseph Hospital, Orange has implemented the role of an ACNP within an ICU step down unit. The role of the ACNP is to provide support to the unit for patient care and staff education. One of the primary functions of the role is to serve as the lead and conduct MDRs on a daily basis, Monday through Friday, for all patients admitted to the unit. As this is a new role for the hospital, the role of the ACNP in conducting MDRs and value added benefit are not well understood. This project will evaluate the role of the ACNP as the lead for MDRs in the step-down unit by identifying specific tasks performed by the ACNP during MDRs that lead to practice improvements related to patient outcomes. Knowledge gained will provide information regarding role definition of the ACNP in MDRs, as well as assist in identification of specific process interventions as they relate to patient outcomes.

The following question will help to guide this project: What are the specific process interventions performed by the ACNP during MDRs in an intensive care step-down unit?

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

A review of the literature provided a plethora of articles that evaluated and analyzed the use of the nurse practitioner and impact on patient outcomes. Recently, the research has shifted to include the role of the nurse practitioner as a participant in the transformation of healthcare delivery and improved patient outcomes. The literature review for this project was conducted utilizing Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health (CINAHL), PubMed, MedLine, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar. The databases were accessed via the Pollak Library at California State University, Fullerton and the Burlew Medical Library at St. Joseph Hospital, Orange. The search strategy was developed with support of a research librarian and included the following terms and combinations: nurse practitioner, intensive care unit, patient outcomes, acute care nurse practitioner, core measures, evidenced based practice, step-down unit, multidisciplinary rounds, and interprofessional practice. The search was limited to articles written in the English language and published within the past 5–7 years, unless considered a landmark study for review.

After an exhaustive search, many articles were systematically identified and evaluated. Several studies provided meaningful evidence to pioneer this project. The findings from the literature review reveal a gap in support of the ACNP as the lead of MDRs in relation to measurable patient outcomes. Research is lacking to understand the process role of the ACNP as the lead of MDRs.

METHODS

The primary objective of this project was to evaluate the role of an ACNP as the lead for MDRs in an ICU step-down unit to better understand process contributions related to patient care outcomes. Through identification of specific tasks performed by the ACNP during MDRs, distinct contributions of the ACNP activities in relation to patient outcomes were identified. Patient outcomes were evaluated to determine the impact of the role of the ACNP in the ICU step-down unit. The following is the methodology and evaluation plan utilized for implementation of this project.

Sample

This project did not involve a human population for study. The researcher self-evaluated the role of the ACNP as the lead in MDRs in an ICU step-down unit.

Setting

This project evaluated the role of the ACNP as the lead provider for MDRs in an intensive care step-down unit at St. Joseph Hospital, Orange. St. Joseph Hospital is a 525-bed acute care facility located within Orange County. The hospital is a Catholic-based institution that extends the traditions of healing of the Sisters of St. Joseph of Orange and has dutifully served the community for over 80 years (St. Joseph Hospital, n.d.). It is part of the tenth largest not-for-profit health system in the nation and was responsible for over 21,000 patient discharges in 2009 (St. Joseph Hospital, n.d.). As part of a strategic plan for improved patient outcomes St. Joseph Hospital has embarked on a commitment to provide perfect care to each and every patient it serves (St. Joseph Hospital, n.d.).

The definitive step-down unit (DSU) is a 20-bed intensive care step-down unit located at St. Joseph Hospital which officially opened in July of 2013. The impetus for the opening of this unit began in January of 2013 wherein a 10-bed intensive care step-down unit was developed as part of a pilot project for the implementation of the first ICU step-down unit at St. Joseph Hospital. With the success of the pilot project, the DSU was then expanded to a full 20-bed step down unit to meet the needs of the hospital in July of 2013. Patients admitted to this unit have either progressed in care to be stable enough for transfer out of the ICU or have a higher level of acuity necessitating closer monitoring but who do not meet admission criteria to the ICU. This unit accepts all inpatient diagnosis with the exception of new-onset acute respiratory failure, hemodynamic instability necessitating multiple vasopressors, intra-aortic balloon pump monitoring, intracranial pressure monitoring, severe sepsis, immediate post-operative open heart surgery, continuous renal replacement therapy, and patients on hypothermia protocol.

As an ICU step-down unit, the DSU is an open unit wherein any physician may admit the patient and serve as the attending physician, guiding the patient's care. The average daily patient census for the DSU ranges from 15–20 patients. During the pilot study, it was identified that this unit was typically a high volume unit with moderate patient turn-over, due to the complexity of the patients. It was recommended that MDRs occur within this unit, similar to the model already employed with the ICU. The role of the ACNP as a lead for MDRs was introduced at the conclusion of the pilot study and with the official opening of the DSU to ensure consistent and timely assessments of patient conditions, evaluations, and transitions. The DSU served as the location for this project evaluation

Measures

In an attempt to measure process outcomes of the ACNP role, specific tasks performed by the ACNP during MDR were tracked over a set timeframe. An Excel spreadsheet entitled “DSU Nurse Practitioner Multidisciplinary Rounds Task Sheet” was utilized to track the specific activities employed (see Appendix A). These areas included various tasks related to scope of practice components of the ACNP including diagnostic activities, planning activities, care-related activities, and co-ordination of activities. Further, these tasks incorporated the specific CMS core measures and clinical indicators for VBP in attempt to reflect the Perfect Care initiatives supported by the institution. Some of the identified measures included appropriate medications or contraindications for AMI and HF patients, as well as SCIP. Additional measures included glucose control, venous thromboembolism (VTE) screening, as well as VTE prophylaxis. The identified tasks served as a process measurement in evaluation of the ACNP role in the DSU. Each intervention(s) performed was tracked according to a de-identified patient number (1–20) for the day. As the patient volume and demographics changed on a daily basis because of high turnover and transition to higher or lower levels of care, the tasks performed were tracked as encounters rather than number of patients.

Data was collected on core measure performance for AMI, HF, SCIP, and immunizations. The number of failures for the core measure items specific to the DSU, were also tracked and evaluated as an outcome measurement. This data was obtained from the St. Joseph Hospital Quality Management Department. The timeframe for data review occurred from 2012 to 2013 and 2013 to 2014.

Tools

In the development of the “DSU Nurse Practitioner Multidisciplinary Rounds Task Sheet” the tasks of the ACNP were developed as most representative of the common intervention categories performed by nurse practitioners, including but not limited to, diagnostic activities, planning activities, care-related activities, and coordination of activities. Core measure categories were developed from actual review of the core measures and specific clinical indicators for acute myocardial infarction, heart failure, surgical care improvement process, and immunizations developed and defined by CMS.

Procedures

MDRs in the DSU occurred on a daily basis, Monday through Friday, on each patient admitted to the unit. Rounds began at 11:00 a.m. until completion and typically lasted 60–90 minutes on average. Rounds did not occur on the weekends, Saturday or Sunday, because of scheduling. MDRs were led by a designated ACNP, and other participants included the patient nurse, the unit clinical coordinator and/or charge nurse, respiratory therapy, infection control, dietary services, case management, and pastoral services. The family members of patients were invited to participate if able. A standardized report was provided by the patient care nurse, with a subsequent roundtable discussion from the team members present regarding the particular patient’s progression of care, identified needs, and plan for the day. Patient issues identified by the team were addressed by the ACNP concurrently. During MDRs, the ACNP utilized the “DSU Nurse Practitioner Multidisciplinary Rounds Task Sheet” to track the activities performed and care issues addressed for each patient during rounds. Since rounds did not occur on

the weekends, the day of the week (Monday through Friday) was tracked as well to evaluate trends between increased need for interventions and the day of the week. This was done on a daily basis over the course of a 3 month time frame which extended from October 1, 2013 to December 31, 2103.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were employed to describe the results for measurements of ACNP tasks performed during MDRs. Distribution categories by the percentage of tasks completed by the ACNP were calculated. In the evaluation of core measure performance, aggregate data collected by the Quality Management Department was reviewed and assessed for outlier cases. All data was input and evaluated using SPSS 20 for statistical analysis.

Data Privacy

Any and all data records utilized for this project were placed in a locked file cabinet in the primary investigator's personal office located at St. Joseph Hospital. Once data was entered into a computer database, the data files were kept on a password-protected computer assigned only to the investigator.

Risks and Benefits

There were minimal risks associated with this project. Collection of anonymous, de-identified data for patient outcomes and observation behaviors of the ACNP were utilized. One risk identified was the increased length of time required to conduct MDRs to allocate for additional time for the ACNP to complete the task. Potential identified benefits of the project included the opportunity to evaluate the role of the ACNP as the lead of MDRs and gain a better understanding of the process activities related to patient

outcomes. Through better definition of the role in relation to outcomes there is potential to extend the ACNP led MDRs to other units of the hospital.

Ethical Considerations

This project did not involve human subjects, and as such the project did not expose any individuals to discomfort or distress; this project did not utilize interviews or surveys of any individuals for this project. The data for core measure performance for the project was de-identified, aggregated data, specific to the DSU unit, but was not identifiable in any way that could link to specific patient visits to the DSU. This project qualified as exempt under the St. Joseph Hospital Institutional Review Board and the California State University, Los Angeles Institutional Review Board.

RESULTS

During the evaluation period, 722 patient encounters occurred during MDRs. Of these, 609 encounters (89%) resulted in a concurrent specific issue(s) that was identified during MDRs, requiring intervention by the ACNP. These tasks related to specific interventions to optimize patient care or interventions related directly to the core measures. Of the identified issues presented during MDRs, a majority of the interventions initiated by the ACNP centered on care coordination activities of physical therapy (21%), occupational therapy (18%), speech therapy (10%), out-patient referral programs (22%), and home health orders (21%). Further, of the 722 encounters, over 90% of the patients had daily goals developed by the care team that focused on plan of care and care coordination strategies. An additional 183 encounters (25%) resulted in discussion and communication with patient family members addressing their specific questions and concerns. Additionally, staff education during MDRs occurred in nearly half (47%) of the encounters for the evaluation period.

Table 1

Task Interventions

Interventions	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Foley Cath Removal Order	120	20.1	20.1	20.1
Central Line Removal Order	54	9.0	9.0	29.1
GI Prophylaxis Order	126	21.1	21.1	50.3
VTE Screen	33	5.5	5.5	55.8
VTE Pharm Order	20	3.4	3.4	59.1
VTE Mech Order	97	16.2	16.2	75.4
Glucose Control	147	24.6	24.6	100.0
Total	597	100.0	100.0	

Additional care process interventions were identified in 597 of the patient encounters. They were identified as orders for Foley catheter removal, which comprised 20% of the interventions, as well as orders for central line removal (9%). Of these patient encounters, a majority of the interventions were focused on gastrointestinal (GI) prophylaxis orders (21%), and VTE mechanical orders (16%). One key area also included 147 encounters (25%) requiring glucose control orders.

Table 2

Encounters by Weekday

Weekday	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Monday	154	21.3	21.3	21.3
Tuesday	139	19.3	19.3	40.6
Wednesday	129	17.9	17.9	58.4
Thursday	144	19.9	19.6	78.4
Friday	156	21.6	21.6	100.0
Total	722	100.0	100.0	

Over a two month time frame, most of the encounters that required interventions occurred on Mondays and Fridays. Of the 722 encounters, nearly half (42%) of the encounters occurred on Mondays or Fridays and the need for interventions were equally distributed between these two days.

Clinical Outcomes by Core Measure

In addition to tracking specific interventions related to optimization of patient care, interventions related to specific core measures for quality purposes were also identified. Figure 3 depicts the distribution of diagnostic categories by percentages of the evaluated encounters identified as having either a primary, secondary, or history of a core measure diagnosis during the MDRs. Of the 722 patient encounters, a total of 183

encounters were identified as core measure incidents with 36% identified as AMI, 32% identified as HF, and an additional 32% identified as SCIP.

Figure 2. Distribution of diagnostic categories by core measure.

In evaluating the specific interventions for each core measure, 65 AMI encounters with issues were identified during MDRs (see Figure 3). A documented contraindication was necessary for the angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor (ACE) or angiotensin II receptor blocker (ARB) medications (22%), and statin medications (22%) in the identified AMI encounters during MDRs. An Aspirin order was necessary in 16% of the patient encounters and 10% of the encounters required an ACE/ARB medication to be ordered.

Figure 3. Acute myocardial infarction core measure interventions.

In evaluation of the HF components, a total of 59 encounters were identified. Of those, 20 encounters (34%) required a documented contraindication for ACE/ARB administration and an additional 42 encounters (71%) resulted in orders being generated for referral to the outpatient heart failure clinic.

There were 59 encounters identified as SCIP. Twenty of those encounters required a home beta-blocker order (3%), 14 required a home beta-blocker contraindication (2%), 38 required a Foley catheter removal contraindication (5.3%), and 15 required a Foley catheter removal order (2%). None of the encounters required documentation for a contraindication to continue the post-operative antibiotics or an order to continue post-operative antibiotics beyond the specified time frame measure.

Although additional tasks were tracked, they were not reported, because of a low percentage rate identified, less than 5%. These tasks included admission status order and clarification, swallow evaluation, labs ordered, therapeutics ordered, diagnostic testing

ordered, and case management ordered. Additionally, the core measure tasks that were tracked and not reported, because of a low percentage included beta blocker contraindication documented, post-operative antibiotics discontinuation and contraindication, pneumonia and influenza vaccinations, as well as issues identified and deferred to the attending physician.

Quality Review Core Measures

Review of the metrics tracked by the Quality Department at St. Joseph Hospital from July 2013 to December 2013 revealed a total of 49 patients identified with a primary diagnosis of AMI (23), HF (16), and SCIP (10). Quality core measure performance was assessed through tabulations of success at or failure to satisfy each individual core measure requirement and then grouped into the appropriate category of AMI, HF, or SCIP. Of these patients, only one identified outcome measure for a HF patient was reported as a failure during this six month time frame (see Figure 5). This was calculated as a 2% failure rate in the total observed core measure patients specific to the DSU patient population. Baseline data for the 6 month time frame observed revealed a 98% compliance rate for all eligible patients who receive specific evidence-based interventions for AMI, HF, and SCIP.

Figure 4. DSU core measure compliance.

Although the Quality Department tracks additional core measure metrics, including pneumonia and stroke patients, those metrics were not included as part of this study for evaluation purposes. However, review of the data with the inclusion of the two additional metrics of pneumonia and stroke revealed a total patient count of 82, with a 99% compliance rate for all eligible patients within the DSU.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this project was to evaluate the role of the ACNP as the lead for MDRs in an ICU step-down unit. Through a detailed analysis of the specific tasks and interventions performed by the ACNP during MDRs, specific identifiers unique to the role of the ACNP were observed. Of particular interest was the evaluation of the process elements described by Sidani and Irvine (2009) in the conceptual framework for ACNP role evaluation. Through identification of the specific role components and role enactment of the ACNP during MDRs, an understanding of the process contributions to clinical outcomes emerged. In this evaluation, the ACNP as the lead for MDRs facilitated several areas of key interest, including coordination of care delivery, education of staff, and adherence to core measure outcomes for the patient population within the DSU.

Coordination of care delivery was operationalized through the interventions that focused on early identification and assessment of functional status and potential transitional needs, including appropriate outpatient referrals, home health, as well as physical, occupational, and speech therapy evaluations and treatment. These interventions were aimed at early identification of patient needs and optimization of patient function for both inpatient and discharge needs. This facilitation of care coordination and transitional care planning has been shown to reduce readmission rates by one third, and also decreases length of stay by 1–2 days (Masica et al., 2009).

Additional interventions included measures aimed at decreasing complications. These measures were operationalized through active VTE screenings and prophylaxis, continual assessment for the need of Foley catheters and central lines including orders to

discontinue them, as well as GI prophylaxis, and glucose control. Complications from these measures include increased morbidity and mortality rates related to the development of deep venous thrombosis, surgical site infections related to hyperglycemia, and infections from devices associated with central lines and Foley catheters. Through identification of the issues during the MDRs encounter, the ACNP was able to address the measures aimed at decreasing complications and order or document the appropriate intervention. Prevention of the complications associated with these measures have shown improved patient outcomes, decreased risk of death, and shortened length of stay (Masica et al., 2009).

In relation to patient outcomes, the goals and expectations of the ACNP role in MDRs were to increase quality of care. In examining the data related to the core measure outcomes from this evaluation, it is clear that while patient outcomes are multifaceted; there were direct instances in which the ACNP directly impacted performance on the core measure outcomes assessed. For the purposes of this evaluation, the outcomes were operationalized as the number of success and failures for the three core measures assessed for AMI, HF, and SCIP. Over a 6 month time frame, only one eligible patient was considered a failure which led to a 98% compliance rate. Further, there were a number of encounters identified in MDRs that addressed core measure variables and variances in standards of care. The ACNP, through the unique provider and prescriptive authority was able to determine the appropriate standard for those variances and select the pertinent intervention for that encounter, this occurred in a concurrent process, as opposed to the issue being identified and brought to the attention of the attending physician at later time. In evaluating the number of success patients on core measure

performance, the use of the ACNP as the lead for MDRs further provided that patients with identified variances from standards of care related to the core measures had appropriate interventions leading to improved compliance within the DSU unit. The utilization of the ACNP ensured adherence to national standardized performance measurements which serve as the basis for the VBP and pay-for-performance initiatives.

An additional component that emerged from this evaluation included the role of the ACNP as an educator. This was operationalized through the high percentage of encounters that resulted in education of staff during MDRs. Observed educational activities included identification of knowledge gaps from the team participants in areas regarding particular disease and pathology, clinical course of treatment, protocol review, and expected clinical outcomes. Although the structure of MDRs was not intended to serve as an educational forum, if particular knowledge deficits were identified, they were addressed. Through the combined role of educator and practitioner, the ACNP also engaged in multiple encounters with patient family members answering questions or conveying the plan of care. This component of the ACNP role has been operationalized as patient outcomes that increase satisfaction with care through enhanced knowledge of staff, the patients, and their families (Sidani & Irvine, 2009).

Although patient outcomes are multifaceted, four process mechanisms of the ACNP role have been proposed that impact the direct care component on patient outcomes. Those mechanisms include provision of comprehensive care, ensuring continuity of care, coordination of services, and providing care in a timely manner (Sidani & Irvine, 2009). Through a clear understanding of the outcome mechanisms of the ACNP role, the impact of NP care on patient outcomes can be further evaluated. This

occurs through promotion of patient access to care, reduction in complications, improved patient knowledge, and patient satisfaction (Newhouse et al., 2011). Exploration of the key functions of the NP provides further insight into ways in which the impact on outcomes can be maximized (Kapu & Kleinpell, 2013). This evaluation has demonstrated a clear link between the specific role functions of the ACNP, as the lead for MDRs, in relation to patient outcomes and VBP components. Even though much research has been done to focus NP performance to other care providers, there is little information to support the unique contributions of the NP role in relation to quality of care measures and patient outcomes specific to the practice of the NP (Kapu & Kleinpell, 2013; Sidani & Irvine, 2009). This evaluation serves as the foundational basis for understanding the components of the NP role and the impact on outcomes specific to VBP measures.

Recommendations

As healthcare is shifting to a pay-for-performance model, institutions across the nation are challenged with developing a comprehensive approach to improve quality outcomes for their patients. The use of MDRs has proved effective in achieving quality in VBP, core measures, patient satisfaction, as well as decreased rates of complications, and overall hospital costs. Whereas MDRs have traditionally been limited to the ICU setting, an innovative practice is the extension of MDRs outside of the ICU to other acute level units. With this increased potential for growth, there is growing concern that an inability to meet these demands exists. The utilization of a NP is emerging as a means to meet this demand and an innovative tactic involves the use of an ACNP as the lead for MDRs. However, for this innovative tactic to be effective, the role components and key

functions of the NP must first be understood, in order to determine the impact on patient outcomes. Through an understanding of the ACNP role as a facilitator to interdisciplinary practice and collaborative care planning, continual evaluation of the impact on patient outcomes can occur. There is potential from this evaluation to extend the use of MDRs to other areas within an acute care setting and utilize the ACNP as the lead for MDRs to ensure continued quality and care coordination. It is therefore recommended that institutions begin to incorporate ACNPs as strategic leaders for MDRs to ensure quality of care and improved coordination of care along the continuum. Institutions should also begin evaluating the value added benefit of extending ACNP led MDRs to other acute care units as a means to achieving high quality of care with a focus on VBP initiatives. This evaluation has demonstrated that the ACNP can play an integral role in driving improvements toward quality of care and serve as an active participant in the restructuring of the healthcare delivery process and outcomes.

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APPENDIX A

DSU NP MULTI-DISCIPLINARY ROUNDS TASK SHEET

Task	Patient 1	Patient 2	Patient 3	Patient 4	Patient 5	Patient 6
Admission Status Order/Clarification						
Physical Therapy Ordered						
Occupational Therapy Ordered						
Speech Therapy Ordered						
Swallow Evaluation Ordered						
Medication Ordered						
Labs Ordered						
Therapeutics Ordered						
Diagnostic Testing Ordered						
VTE Screening						
VTE Mechanical Ordered						
VTE Pharmacological (Lovenox/Heparin) Ordered						
GI Prophylaxis Ordered						
Foley Catheter Removal Ordered						
Central Line Removal Ordered						
Case Management Referral						
Outpatient Program Referrals						
Home Health Ordered						
Core Measures						
AMI						
Aspirin Within 24 Hours of Arrival Ordered						
Aspirin Contraindication Documented						
Statin Therapy Ordered						
Statin Contraindication Documented						
Beta Blocker Therapy Ordered						
Beta Blocker Contraindication Documented						
ACE/ARB Ordered						

Task	Patient 1	Patient 2	Patient 3	Patient 4	Patient 5	Patient 6
HF						
LV Function Documented						
ACE/ARB Therapy Ordered						
ACE/ARB Contraindication Documented						
CHF Referral to Outpatient Clinic						
SCIP						
Home BB Ordered Postoperatively						
Home BB Contraindication Documented						
Removal of Foley Catheter by POD # 2						
Removal of Foley Catheter Contraindication Documented						
Post-operative Antibiotics Discontinued by POD # 2						
Post-operative Antibiotics Contraindication Documented						
Pneumonia Vaccine						
Ordered						
Contraindication Documented						
Influenza Vaccine						
Ordered						
Contraindication Documented						
Other						
Set Daily Goals for Patient						
Education of Staff						
Answer Family Questions						
Issue Deferred to Attending Physician						

Task	Patient 7	Patient 8	Patient 9	Patient 10	Patient 11
Admission Status Order/Clarification					
Physical Therapy Ordered					
Occupational Therapy Ordered					
Speech Therapy Ordered					
Swallow Evaluation Ordered					
Medication Ordered					
Labs Ordered					
Therapeutics Ordered					
Diagnostic Testing Ordered					
VTE Screening					
VTE Mechanical Ordered					
VTE Pharmacological (Lovenox/Heparin) Ordered					
GI Prophylaxis Ordered					
Foley Catheter Removal Ordered					
Central Line Removal Ordered					
Case Management Referral					
Outpatient Program Referrals					
Home Health Ordered					
Core Measures					
AMI					
Aspirin Within 24 Hours of Arrival Ordered					
Aspirin Contraindication Documented					
Statin Therapy Ordered					
Statin Contraindication Documented					
Beta Blocker Therapy Ordered					
Beta Blocker Contraindication Documented					
ACE/ARB Ordered					
ACE/ARB Contraindication					

Task	Patient 12	Patient 13	Patient 14	Patient 15	Patient 16	Patient 17
Admission Status Order/Clarification						
Physical Therapy Ordered						
Occupational Therapy Ordered						
Speech Therapy Ordered						
Swallow Evaluation Ordered						
Medication Ordered						
Labs Ordered						
Therapeutics Ordered						
Diagnostic Testing Ordered						
VTE Screening						
VTE Mechanical Ordered						
VTE Pharmacological (Lovenox/Heparin) Ordered						
GI Prophylaxis Ordered						
Foley Catheter Removal Ordered						
Central Line Removal Ordered						
Case Management Referral						
Outpatient Program Referrals						
Home Health Ordered						
Core Measures						
AMI						
Aspirin Within 24 Hours of Arrival Ordered						
Aspirin Contraindication Documented						
Statin Therapy Ordered						
Statin Contraindication Documented						
Beta Blocker Therapy Ordered						
Beta Blocker Contraindication Documented						
ACE/ARB Ordered						
ACE/ARB Contraindication						

Task	Patient 12	Patient 13	Patient 14	Patient 15	Patient 16	Patient 17
HF						
LV Function Documented						
ACE/ARB Therapy Ordered						
ACE/ARB Contraindication Documented						
CHF Referral to Outpatient Clinic						
SCIP						
Home BB Ordered Postoperatively						
Home BB Contraindication Documented						
Removal of Foley Catheter by POD # 2						
Removal of Foley Catheter Contraindication Documented						
Post-operative Antibiotics Discontinued by POD # 2						
Post-operative Antibiotics Contraindication Documented						
Pneumonia Vaccine						
Ordered						
Contraindication Documented						
Influenza Vaccine						
Ordered						
Contraindication Documented						
Other						
Set Daily Goals for Patient						
Education of Staff						
Answer Family Questions						
Issue Deferred to Attending Physician						

Task	Patient 18	Patient 19	Patient 20
Admission Status Order/Clarification			
Physical Therapy Ordered			
Occupational Therapy Ordered			
Speech Therapy Ordered			
Swallow Evaluation Ordered			
Medication Ordered			
Labs Ordered			
Therapeutics Ordered			
Diagnostic Testing Ordered			
VTE Screening			
VTE Mechanical Ordered			
VTE Pharmacological (Lovenox/Heparin) Ordered			
GI Prophylaxis Ordered			
Foley Catheter Removal Ordered			
Central Line Removal Ordered			
Case Management Referral			
Outpatient Program Referrals			
Home Health Ordered			
Core Measures			
AMI			
Aspirin Within 24 Hours of Arrival Ordered			
Aspirin Contraindication Documented			
Statin Therapy Ordered			
Statin Contraindication Documented			
Beta Blocker Therapy Ordered			
Beta Blocker Contraindication Documented			
ACE/ARB Ordered			
ACE/ARB Contraindication			

Task	Patient 18	Patient 19	Patient 20
HF			
LV Function Documented			
ACE/ARB Therapy Ordered			
ACE/ARB Contraindication Documented			
CHF Referral to Outpatient Clinic			
SCIP			
Home BB Ordered Postoperatively			
Home BB Contraindication Documented			
Removal of Foley Catheter by POD # 2			
Removal of Foley Catheter Contraindication Documented			
Post-operative Antibiotics Discontinued by POD # 2			
Post-operative Antibiotics Contraindication Documented			
Pneumonia Vaccine			
Ordered			
Contraindication Documented			
Influenza Vaccine			
Ordered			
Contraindication Documented			
Other			
Set Daily Goals for Patient			
Education of Staff			
Answer Family Questions			
Issue Deferred to Attending Physician			

APPENDIX B

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD APPROVALS

Office Memorandum

DATE: March 14, 2014

TO: Thomas W. Barkley, Jr./Lisa Evans
Nursing, NSS

FROM: E. Amaro, Institutional Review Board – Human Subjects

COPIES TO: S. Ulanoff, Chair; J. Shiotsugu, Executive Secretary

SUBJECT: Review of Project Involving Human Subjects

Applicant: Thomas W. Barkley, Jr./Lisa Evans

Title: Evaluation of an Acute Care Nurse Practitioner's Role in Leading
Multidisciplinary Rounds in an Intensive Care Step-Down Unit

Application #: IRB W13-5

Date of Review: November 18, 2013

Action: Approved 1/7/14
 Convened committee
 Expedited (reviewed and approved by IRB chair or designee)
 Denied - see below
 Tabled - see below
 Administrative Action Waiver
 Informed Consent:

**SJH Human Research Protections Program
DETERMINATION OF NON-HUMAN SUBJECT RESEARCH**

Federal regulations and SJH policies require IRB review of research involving human subjects. Activities that meet the regulatory definitions of "research" and "human subjects" constitute human subject research and require IRB approval and oversight, except in cases of exempt research.

Project Title: <u>Evaluation of Nurse Practitioner Led Multi-Disciplinary Rounds in a Step Down Unit</u>
Investigator: <u>Lisa Evans, NP</u>

DETERMINATION OF "RESEARCH"
45 CFR 46.102(d):
<i>Research - a systematic investigation, including research development, testing and evaluation, designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge.</i>
<p>1. Do the proposed activities involve a <i>systematic investigation</i>? A "systematic" approach involves a predetermined method or a plan for studying a specific topic, answering a specific question, testing a specific hypothesis, or developing theory. A systematic approach incorporates collection of data, either quantitative or qualitative, or specimens; and analysis.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES* <input type="checkbox"/> NO**</p> <p>**If NO, please explain why the proposed activities do not involve a systematic approach: _____</p>
<p>2. Is the intent of the proposed activities to develop or contribute to <i>generalizable knowledge</i>? Activities designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge are those activities designed to draw general conclusions, inform policy, or generalize findings beyond a single individual or internal program.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES* <input type="checkbox"/> NO**</p> <p>**If NO, please explain the intent of proposed activities and explain how the proposed activities are not intended to contribute to generalizable knowledge: _____</p> <p align="center">*If YES to both of the above questions, these activities constitute research.</p>

DETERMINATION OF "HUMAN SUBJECT"	
45 CFR 46.102(f):	
<p>Human subject - a <i>living individual</i> about whom an investigator (whether faculty, student, or staff) conducting research obtains: (1) data through <i>intervention or interaction</i> with the individual or (2) <i>identifiable private information</i>.</p> <p>Intervention includes both physical procedures by which data are gathered (for example, venipuncture) and manipulations of the subject or the subject's environment that are performed for research purposes.</p> <p>Interaction includes communication or interpersonal contact between researcher and subject.</p> <p>Private information includes information about behavior that occurs in a context in which an individual can reasonably expect that no observation or recording is taking place (such as a public restroom), and information which has been provided for specific purposes by an individual and which the individual can reasonably expect will not be made public (for example, medical record information). Private information must be individually identifiable.</p> <p>Individually identifiable means the identity of the subject is or may readily be ascertained by the investigator or associated with the information; the data contains one or more data elements that can be combined with other reasonably available information to identify an individual (i.e. at least one of the 18 identifiers under the HIPAA Privacy Rule, if an investigator can readily ascertain the identity of the individual).</p>	
<p>1. Do the activities involve obtaining information about <i>living individuals</i>? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>1a. If "Yes" to Question 1, do the activities involve intervention or interaction with the individuals (i.e., prospective collection of data/specimens) for research purposes that are not otherwise conducted for standard medical care? <input type="checkbox"/> YES* <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO**</p> <p>*If YES, the activities involve human subjects. **If NO, the activities DO NOT involve human subjects.</p>	
<p>2. Do the activities involve obtaining <i>individually identifiable</i> and <i>private</i> information about living individuals? <input type="checkbox"/> YES* <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO**</p> <p>*If YES, the activities involve human subjects. **If NO, the activities DO NOT involve human subjects.</p>	
<p>3. Do the activities involve analysis of existing <i>data/specimens</i> (i.e., data/specimens have been collected and are available for analysis)? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>3a. If "yes" to Question 3, will the <i>data/specimens</i> be coded such that a link exists that could allow the source of the data/specimens to be re-identified (i.e., key available to decipher the code)? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO</p> <p>3b. If "yes" to Question 3a, is there a written agreement that prohibits the Lead Researcher and his/her research team from having access to the link? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO**</p> <p>**If you answered YES to 3 and 3a and NO to 3b, these activities involve human subjects.</p>	

DETERMINATION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS RESEARCH	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The activities as described DO NOT constitute Human Subjects Research. Submission of an IRB Application is not required.
<input type="checkbox"/>	The activities as described DO constitute Human Subjects Research. Submission of an IRB Application IS REQUIRED . IRB Approval must be obtained before the research can begin.
Reviewer: <u>Mary Parga, CIP</u>	
Date of review: <u>9/3/2013</u>	
Comments: <u>The study involves using a de-identified data source that only includes aggregate data.</u>	

APPENDIX C

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